

Inventories & Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH)

Survey Data - Digital ICH Observatory

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Between May and June 2020, the DIGITAL ICH Observatory conducted the survey "Inventories & Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH)". With this data we intended to analyse the practices and opinions of users of ICH Inventories.

The 2003 UNESCO Convention underlines the importance of ICH inventories to safeguard, disseminate, and raise awareness on ICH. All nominations for inscription in the ICH World Lists must be included on an ICH Inventory. Mostly for this reason, in the last 12 years, multiple processes of inventory have begun. Nevertheless, how are ICH inventories being used? How do users consult them? What opinion do they have about them? To answer these and other questions we applied this survey. Now we present the results of this work, starting by describing the sample studied in the research.

Sample Characterisation

95,9% Academic degree
4,1% High school

246 individuals responded to the survey, 61,8% women and 38,2% men. The majority are aged 41-60 (54,9%), but also answered the questionnaire the age groups 21-40 (28%) and 61+ (17,1%) (figs. 1-2). About 96% of individuals have an academic degree (associate, bachelor, master, or doctoral) and 87,4% are employed. Only 4,1% are studying, 8,1% are retired, and 0,4% are unemployed (fig. 3-4). 71,1% of respondents reside in an urban area and 28,9% in a rural area (fig.5).

Fig. 6 - Relation to Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH).

Among respondents, 78% refer that they relate to Intangible Cultural Heritage because they work or study on this subject; 14,3% are ICH practitioners, and 7,7% are just curious about ICH issues (not practising, working, or studying on ICH)¹ (fig.6).

Fig. 7 - Entity of work.

Figs. 1,2,3,4,5 - Sex, age, school qualification, activity and residence.

¹ In this question, respondents could only choose one option. For instance, if they studied on ICH and were also practitioners, they had to select the item that best characterised their present situation, the one with which they most identified.

Considering the respondents who work, about 88,8% are in public administration or education, science and culture services, performing intellectual and scientific professions (65,1%) or working in administrative (19,1%) or technical functions (10,6%). Only 4,7% are entrepreneurs, and 0,5% have no professional qualification. 42,2% work at the State (national administration - 25,4% - regional or local administration - 16,8%); 24,1% work at universities and research centres; 21,6% at NGOs and 12,1% at the private sector (fig.7).

Fig. 8 - World Region

Concerning geographic distribution, there is a higher Europe representation of respondents (70,7%), followed by Asia and the Pacific (13,4%), Africa (7,7%), the Latin America and the Caribbean region (6,5%) and, lastly, the Arab States (1,7%) (fig.8).

Sample Process

The sampling process was based on the non-probabilistic Snowball technique and data collection was carried out online, i.e., the survey link (Google forms) was sent to an international mailing list of about 1000 individuals² related to Intangible Cultural Heritage (researchers, practitioners, students, representatives of communities, professionals who work at State entities, at NGOs and other institutions). The questionnaire was also disseminated by social media, namely Facebook, newsletters and websites. All contacts were informed that they could spread the survey among their relevant contacts (related to ICH).

Sample critique

With the Snowball technique, which does not allow results generalisation, we only can describe the outcomes considering the sample, and because we do not know precisely how many people received the survey, we cannot calculate the response rate. However, on the one hand, on a theoretical exercise, considering the first 1000 contacts and the 246 responses we have a satisfactory rate of 24,6% (considering that the average of return for online surveys is 5%-30%).³ We can also consider 246 respondents a reasonable number to support the planned data analysis - a descriptive analysis restricted to the sample without extrapolation to the universe (individuals related to ICH). On the other hand,

² Mailing list built in the last ten years by the NGO Memória Imaterial through contacts with other ICH NGOs, UNESCO, nominations for World Lists, entities producing ICH Inventories, representative communities and others. The survey was anonymous, no identity information was requested, respondents were informed that the data collected would only be used for statistical treatment. The filling time was, on average, less than 15 minutes.

³ <https://www.customerthermometer.com/customer-surveys/average-survey-response-rate/>; <https://surveyanyplace.com/average-survey-response-rate/>; <https://surveysparrow.com/blog/what-is-a-good-survey-response-rate-indeed-heres-the-answer-we-found/> [consulted 25-06-2020].

since it is not possible to define the exact number of people who, worldwide, are related to ICH, the limitations of a non-probabilistic sample must be put into perspective. In the absence of accurate data about this population, it will be impossible to guarantee a representative sample, even if we used a random process.

Considering the main characteristics of the sample, we can assume that the sampling has some bias: the majority of the respondents are European, with higher education, working as professionals or specialists in the field of social science, culture and ICH. However, if we look to the context of the ICH processes (not to the cultural practices but the patrimonialization process) the bias already exists in the "real world". We think that the sample represents those who, nowadays, are actually related to ICH's patrimonialization processes: individuals who are familiar with the concept of ICH, the 2003 UNESCO Convention and the UNESCO recommendations - the European experts and professionals that contributed to the Convention construction and its implementation (see graphics.1 and 2, page 6).

About the higher European representation, we come across it in different aspects of the ICH processes: the largest number of national e-Inventories are European (Sousa, 2017); a significant amount of elements registered in the Representative List are from Europe; a considerable number of ICH NGOs accredited by UNESCO are European, among other aspects.

However, it is crucial that we are aware of this bias - the Europe-centric view in ICH's patrimonialization processes -, and since we will try to understand the involvement of different individuals, groups and communities in these processes, we consider convenient, for some analysis, to recode the variables "Region" and "Relation to ICH". So, to slightly increase their statistical relevance and the possibility to better characterise them, the "other regions" of the world will be recoded as a whole (fig.9), and "ICH practitioners and curious about ICH" will also be aggregated in a single category (fig.10).

Fig. 9 - World Region recoded.

Fig. 10 - Relation to ICH recoded.

About the two recoded variables, we can find slight differences when compared with the general sample. Analysing "practitioners/curious about ICH" and those "who work/study on ICH", there is a higher percentage of residents in rural areas among the first group (53,7% versus 21,9%). It is also among those who practice ICH that there is a higher percentage of workers in "administrative and technical functions" (44,5% compared to 26,3%) and less "intellectual and scientific professions" (37,8% versus 71,6%). This group is also characterised by more employees in the "private sector" (34,8%) and "retired" people (18,5%) (table.1).

		Rural residence	Adm + Tech	Intellect. scientific	Private Sector	Retired
Relation to ICH	Practice ICH + Curious	53,7%	44,5%	37,8%	34,8%	18,5%
	Work or study on ICH	21,9%	26,3%	71,6%	6,5%	5,2%

Table 1 - Relation to ICH recoded/rural residence/profession/work entity and

Regarding the "Region", the most distinctive characteristic seems to be a higher percentage of men respondents in "Other Regions" (56,9% compared to 30,5% in "Europe and North America Region"), there is also a slight increase of "urban residents" in those regions (88,9% versus 63,8%) (table.2).

		Sex Male	Urban residence
Region	Other Regions	56,9%	88,9%
	Europe and North America Region	30,5%	63,8%

Table 2 - Region/male/urban residence

The structure of the survey

The study of practices and opinions of ICH Inventories' users.

After the sociodemographic characterization, the survey addressed three other groups of questions: one relating ICH Inventories and the knowledge on the UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage; a group about the practices of ICH inventories' users - number of inventories consulted; the regularity and time spent on these inventories; inventories' characteristics and types of use (search, content, social networks, types of "interaction"/participation); and finally, the third group on opinions - inventories' evaluation; opinion on the importance of inventories in ICH safeguarding; opinion on what inventories should contain, how they should be structured and how communities, groups or individuals (CGIs) should participate in them.⁴

Practices - ICH Inventories and 2003 UNESCO Convention.

About relation to ICH inventories, 90% of those who "work or study on ICH" have already worked on ICH inventories. This group is very familiar with the 2003 UNESCO Convention, 88% "know well or very well" this document (graphic.1). They consult inventories at least once a month, for one or more hours and most of them know 5 to 10 or more inventories.

Among "ICH practitioners and curious about ICH", 48,1% "don't know or badly know" the 2003 UNESCO Convention (graphic.1). Among these, 53,8% have never consulted ICH inventories (graphic.2). If they did it, the frequency is once a year or even less, and for 5 to 30 minutes.

Graphic 1 - Relation to ICH * Do you know the 2003 UNESCO Convention?

⁴ Among the total respondents who have consulted at least one inventory (216).

Graphic 2 - Never consulted an ICH inventory * Relation to ICH * Do you know the 2003 UNESCO Convention?

These values converge to the hypothesis made on the bias that exists in the "world of ICH" - who have more information on ICH are the experts and professionals involved in the implementation of the Convention (see page 3). We cannot forget that the ICH concept was fostered by national and supranational governmental institutions and their experts. Through an etic procedure, these institutions defined legal instruments for the safeguarding of ICH, i.e., this process was not born out of populations' claims or their involvement in these decisions (Leal, 2013; Sousa, 2015). If the UNESCO and some States proclaim the need for direct participation of communities, groups and individual (CGIs) in these processes, in practice, the real involvement is still residual. It starts to be more significant, but much remains to be done to achieve this goal.

Practices - ICH inventories consulted (characterization).

Most frequently, respondents consult inventories in their language (55,6%), in second place are inventories consulted in English (41,2%). Only 3,2% are in other languages, different from English or mother tongue (fig.11).

The majority of inventories consulted have a national scope (55,6%), 19,9% are transnational, having ICH elements from several countries; 17,1% have a regional focus and 7,4% are local (fig. 12).

Most of these inventories have elements from the 5 ICH domains (52,8%), but 15,3% are exclusively dedicated to "social practices, rituals and festive events"; 11,1% to "traditional craftsmanship"; 8,8% to "oral expressions", also 8,8% to "performing arts" and only 3,2% are dedicated to "knowledge and practices concerning nature and the universe" (fig. 13). Most of these inventories have up to 50 inscribed elements (52,9%).

The States promotes 49,1% of the inventories consulted - 34,7% with national management and 14,4% have regional administration -, NGOs promote 25,9% inventories and UNESCO promotes 13,4%. Private individuals promote only 0,5%, and 6,7% are managed by other types of organisations (fig. 14).

In my country's language 55,6%

Figs.11 IHC Inventories' language

55,6% National

Figs.12 IHC Inventories' Geographic level

Inventories consulted: 52.8% about all ICH domains

Fig. 13 - ICH domains in Inventories

Fig. 14 - The Inventory Promoter

Respondents also report that most of the inventories consulted are public (87%), online (79,6%) and open access (73,1%) - what we denominate as "ICH e-Inventories" (Sousa, 2017). Most consider these inventories updated (53,7%), 30% do not know if they are updated, and 17,1% say they are not. The majority do not know if inventories make calls for people's participation or think they do not make it at all (57,4%).

Considering all this characterization and the variable "Relation to ICH", we find two differences comparing those "who work/study on ICH" and "practitioners/curious about ICH": a) the first group consulted more inventories dedicated to all ICH domains and the second group consulted more inventories considering a specific ICH domain - 76,3% versus 41% (graphic.3) (with special incidence in "traditional craftsmanship" and "oral expressions" for the second group); 2) it is also among those who practice ICH that the majority of inventories consulted is not promoted by the States, but by NGOs and other organizations (55,3% versus 44,4%) (graphic.4).

In relation to the "Region", there is a higher number of consulted inventories that are not online in "Other regions" than in "Europe and North America" (32,8% versus 11,2%) (graphic.5).

Graphic 3 - Relation to ICH * ICH Domains on consulted inventories

Graphic 4 - Relation to ICH * Promoters of consulted inventories

Graphic 5 - Region * Inventories consulted online

Evaluation - ICH inventories consulted.

To finish the consulted inventories' characterization, we asked respondents to rate these inventories on a scale between "very bad" and "very good". The results show that, in general, appreciation is positive, standing between "reasonable" (48,1%) and "good" (41,7%). Few people rate the inventories as "bad" (1,4%), and no one considers them "very bad". But also few rate them as "very good" (8,8%), that is, as exemplars (graphic.6).

Graphic 6 – Evaluation of ICH Inventories consulted.

Practices - ICH inventories' types of uses.

Considering how respondents consult inventories, 23 variables were analysed - a range of practices, such as "read texts"; "watch videos", "visit only the front page" of the inventory, "explore multiple pages", "explore by search", "share info on social media", "leave comments", etc. (see questions 24-28 Annex A). For each item, the respondent mentioned the frequency with which he performed these practices: "Never", "Rarely", "Sometimes", "Many times" or "Always".⁵

The results show that, regardless the type of relationship with ICH or sociodemographic data, the majority of individuals (more than 60%) navigate "always or many times" through multiple pages of the inventory, reading information and seeing photos of ICH elements (over 70%). The frequency with which they watch videos or hear soundtracks, being high, decreases slightly compared to the frequency of reading and seeing photos (graphic.7).

Over 60% of respondents say that it is common to know what they are looking for when they consult an ICH inventory. Among those who use the search, about 50% say that "many times or always" use the "simple search", by keyword. "Advanced searches", by location, domain or other criteria, are frequent but decrease compared to "simple search" (referred by 30% to 40% of respondents) (graphic.7).

It should be noted that, despite the frequent browse by inventories' multiple pages (as mentioned above), about 20% of respondents only visit the first page of the inventories, not exploring their contents.

⁵ To increase the statistical relevance, the categories of these variables were recoded in "Never or rarely" (aggregation of "Never" and "Rarely"); "Sometimes" and "Many times or always" (aggregation of "Many times" and "Always").

Graphic 7 - Most frequent practices when consulting an ICH inventory. (Carried out "many times or always" - Variables 24-28).

Considering the other extreme of the frequency scale, we find that respondents rarely "interact" on the inventory platforms or share information consulted on social networks: 50% to 70% of respondents "never or rarely" make comments, leave questions, collaborate in forums, subscribe to "communities" or propose content. Participation through the subscription of newsletters, being equally rare, is a little more frequent. It is also rare to share inventories' information on respondents' social networks or to use the social networks of inventory promoters (graphic.8).

Graphic 8 – Less frequent practices when consulting an ICH inventory. (Carried out "never or rarely" – Variables 26 and 28).

Opinion - ICH inventories' structure and utility.

As already mentioned, in order to understand not only the practices but also the representations on ICH inventorying process, in the last part of the survey, we asked respondents to give their opinion on the importance of inventories in ICH safeguarding; on what information inventories should contain, how they should be structured and how communities, groups or individuals should participate in them. To obtain this opinion, we used the following scale of importance: "Not Important", "Less important", "So-so", "Important", "Very important" and "No opinion".⁶

⁶ To increase the statistical relevance, the categories of these variables were recoded in "Not Important or less important" (aggregation of "Not Important", "Less important" and "So, So"); "Important" and "Very important". In justified situations, the categories "Important" and "Very important" were also added. "No opinion" percentages were very residual and were considered "Missing cases".

Starting with the analysis on opinions about the theme above mentioned - the way respondents "interact" with inventories - it is curious to find a discrepancy between practices and representations. What respondents do differ from what they value. For example, on the one hand, they rarely participate in forums, subscribe communities or use social networks associated with inventories. On the other hand, the majority (between 50% and 85%) consider "important or very important" that the inventories have "contents to share" (84,6%), a "presence on social networks" (75,8%), be "interactive" (75,8%), promote "forums and communities" (64,9%) and provide a "newsletter" (57,3%) (graphic.9).

Graphic 9 – Opinion: What should an ICH inventory have/How should an inventory be? (Variables 33.3 to 33.7 and 32.3)

The discrepancy between practices and opinions can be interpreted in multiple ways. Still, two hypotheses seem evident: respondents value this participation, but the inventories do not provide the necessary tools to achieve it; or respondents theoretically value something that, in practice, they are not available to do ("do what I say, don't do what I do").

The survey results do not allow us to test these hypotheses, this is definitely an issue to develop in future researches. However, if we consider data from the Digital ICH Observatory, and the ICH e-Inventories study (Sousa, 2017), we see that, in 2017, the percentage of inventories that promoted active user interaction was small. For instance, on the use of social networks, in 158 inventories analysed, more than 70% had no presence on social networks. Only 27% had project pages in social media, mostly on Facebook and on Twitter. Of these, only 23% shared videos on YouTube, and only 21% shared photos on Instagram. We can also see that only 12% allowed visitors to share content on their profiles, once again, mostly on Facebook and on Twitter.

Regarding generic characteristics of ICH inventories, practices and representations are more consistent. For instance, as already mentioned, respondents report that most of the inventories consulted are what we called "ICH e-Inventories" - public (87%), online (79,6%) and open access inventories (73,1 %). Analysing the opinions, we found that most of the respondents (60% to 70%) consider "very important" that inventories have these characteristics, that is, they should be public and available to all. They also value updated and searchable information (graphic.10).

Less valued seems to be the "entertaining" aspect of the inventory. Even when 80% to 90% of the respondents consider an "appealing design/layout" and "clear menus" to be essential (graphic.11), 75,5% do not value inventories because they are "funny" (graphic.10) or serve "to enjoy ICH" (graphic.12). Without advocating a total "scientific" attribute, too hermetic or difficult to consult, the practical side of inventories is, however, more valued than the recreational aspect (graphic.10).

Graphic 10 – Opinion: How should an ICH inventory be? (Variables 32)

Graphic 11 – Opinion: What should an ICH inventory have? (Variables 33.1 and 33.2)

Analysing the opinion on the importance of inventories, we found that the majority considers inventories "very important" as a measure to safeguard ICH (71,6%) (graphic.12). However, in line with the mentioned above, inventories are slightly more valued for their "technical" aspects than for their ability to increase practices. Observing the data, we have more respondents considering inventories "very important" "to provide information" (70,8%); "to give ICH visibility" (70,8%), "to archive ICH" (66,5%) than to "increase ICH practitioners" (49,8%) or "to engage people with ICH" (57,2%) (graphic.12).

Graphic 12 – Opinion: Why are ICH inventories important?

Opinion - ICH inventories' contents.

Regarding the contents that must be included in an ICH inventory, considering what respondents consider "very important", the majority (between 51% and 65%) finds the fields "tradition name" and "short description of the tradition" essential. Information that proves the "community consent" to make the inventory, and information that guarantees the "intellectual rights" associated with the ICH elements are also considered "very important" by most respondents (graphic.13).

More detailed and developed information is considered essential for 30% to 50% of respondents: specific information, for example, about ICH practitioners; details on the tradition, historical data, photos, videos, references to risks associated with the practice, a safeguard plan and information on the 2003 UNESCO Convention (graphic.13).

The availability of soundtracks and data on "methodology/team info" in the inventories, being considered important, are not considered as important as the aspects previously mentioned (graphic.13).

Analysing what respondents do not consider important to be in an ICH inventory, new technologies tools for ICH visualisation and fruition are not regarded as essential. For instance, 60% to 70% of the respondents do not give importance to "access to virtual reality/augmented reality", "streaming sessions"⁷ and "360° photos" (graphic.13).

Graphic 13 – Opinion: What information should be available in an ICH inventory?

⁷ This data was collected in 2019, before the COVID 19 pandemic, when the use of streaming sessions, webinars and other web systems were widely used for ICH-related initiatives. We hypothesise that these circumstances may have changed this opinion. However, we cannot confirm that.

Practices and Opinions - ICH inventories' participation.

As we saw before, 53,2% of respondents "never or rarely" propose content for inventories, 57,4% do not know if inventories open calls for participation. However, questioned about what characterises a "participatory inventory", the majority rates as "important or very important" "to use participatory techniques" (90,5%), "to have a call for contributions" (82,6%), "to provide technical support" (93%), "to be easy to fill" (90,5%), "to allow voluntary contributions" (82,6%), "to have moderators" (81,6%) and "to give instructions for contributions" (81,6%) (graphic.14a).

This result takes us back to the study on ICH e-Inventories (Sousa, 2017) which concludes that, among the 158 inventories analysed, the method of participation of the communities, groups and individuals in the inventory process is little detailed, only 22 inventories (14% of the total) announce in a visible way "the character of the collaborative process of inventory and call for the direct participation of the practitioners of cultural expressions, local institutions and other actors involved" (pp. 8).

Graphic 14a – Opinion: What is important in a participatory ICH inventory?

It is also curious to recall that users do not "interact" when navigating on ICH e-Inventories, but if we consider the participation in public actions about ICH inventories, the results are diverse. The majority of respondents (50% to 75%) have already participated in public sessions (71,8%), training actions (71,3%), assemblies (63,4%) and debates whose main subject was the ICH inventory (56,9%) (graphic.14b). On this point, we cannot forget the characteristics of the sample and the fact that 78% of respondents "work or study" in the field of intangible cultural heritage.

Graphic 14b – Participation in ICH public sessions, ICH plenaries and ICH capacity-building/Workshops.

Also related to participatory methodologies is a question about the role of communities, groups and individuals (CGIs) in the inventory processes. Results show that the participation of CGIs in different stages of the process is very well evaluated. However, most of the respondents (50% to 63%) see CGIs especially as "beneficiaries" of the process, or as actors who help "to identify ICH to inventory". Engaging communities, groups and individuals in decision-making or in the inventory management is not as valued as involving them as "informants" (graphic.15).⁸

Considering these results, and the different levels of CGIs engagement in ICH safeguarding (Sousa, 2018),⁹ we can say that respondents are more in line with an "Informative/advisory Level" of participation. It seems that they see CGIs "as beneficiaries and informants, or even as consultants, but without the possibility of deciding or influencing the defined plan". In this case, CGIs are mainly associated with "elementary levels of involvement" participating "for example, by attending information sessions, being interviewed and answering surveys or participating in focus groups" (pp.35).

In fact, almost one-third of the respondents considered that it is "not important or less important" that CGIs have an active role "to manage the inventory process" (33%). Some consider CGIs do not have an important role as advisers (21,3%) or to decide "what and how to inventory" (23%) (graphic.15). That is, "the ideal maximum level" of participation, a "mobilizer advanced level" is not yet unanimously valued. In a "mobilizer advanced level" the initiative of the inventory process begins with the CGIs, and they self-mobilize and manage the project (in partnership with external agents) (Sousa, 2018).

⁸ Whatever the relationship with the ICH or sociodemographic characteristics.

⁹ "Different levels of CGI involvement through the inventory process:

- a) Informative/Advisory Level - external agents define the problems to be solved and the solutions to be implemented, while considering the CGIs only as beneficiaries and informants, or even as consultants, but without the possibility of deciding or influencing the defined plan - for example, by attending information sessions, being interviewed and answering surveys or participating in focus groups. These are elementary levels of involvement;
- b) Advisory/Mobilizer basic level - the CGIs are part of forums, councils, panels or citizens' juries, working meetings and other group dynamics. In this situation they are considered as agents in the inventory process;
- c) Mobilizer basic level - if the collaboration materializes itself in a shared responsibility relationship, in a commitment through which they participate actively in the decisions made, the level of involvement is higher, and the CGIs present themselves as partners and co-authors of the planning. Participation increases if there is an effective implication in the various implementation phases - diagnosis, planning, action and evaluation;
- e) Mobilizer advanced level - the ideal maximum level is achieved when the initiative of the inventory process begins with the CGIs and when, in partnership with external agents, it is the communities, groups and individuals who self-mobilize and manage the project (Adnan et al., 1992; Community Places, 2014; Pretty, 1994)." (Sousa, 2018, pp. 35).

Graphic 15 – Opinion: What should be the role of communities, groups or individuals in ICH inventories?

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